

Studies on Dioxouranium(VI) Complexes with some Schiff Bases

P. S. PRABHU and S. S. DODWAD*

Physical Chemistry Laboratory, Institute of Science, Madame Cama Road, Bombay-400 032

Manuscript received 16 July 1984, revised 30 May 1985, accepted 3 March 1986

Uranyl complexes of some Schiff bases obtained by condensing salicylaldehyde with 2-aminopyridine, aniline and nitroanilines and 5-methylsalicylaldehyde with 2-aminopyridine are synthesised and characterised by elemental analysis, spectral and conductance data and magnetic susceptibility study. All the complexes are orange-red in colour, microcrystalline in nature and form compounds of the type $[\text{UO}_2(\text{LH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $[\text{UO}_2(\text{L})_2]$, where LH and L are Schiff base molecules, L representing the ligand containing pyridyl nitrogen in the structure. The bonding with the metal in the complexes takes place from oxygen and hydroxyl oxygen in the two types of ligands and the imine nitrogen of the ligands. Pyridyl nitrogen does not take part in coordination. The studies show that the complexes formed are 1:2 adducts and that the complexes have coordination number eight and six, respectively.

METAL complexes with Schiff base ligands obtained from salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehyde with various aromatic amines have been extensively studied¹⁻⁵. Solution study of a number of Schiff base complexes with various divalent metal ions have been studied by Dodwad *et al*^{6,7} in this laboratory. The authors have reported uranyl complexes of some Schiff bases elsewhere⁸. In the present investigation, the authors wish to report some more uranyl complexes with different series of Schiff bases.

Experimental

Uranyl nitrate hexahydrate used for preparing the complexes was of AnalaR grade. Salicylaldehyde, 2-aminopyridine, aniline and nitroanilines of L. R. grade were purified by conventional methods. 5-Methylsalicylaldehyde was prepared by the method suggested by Duff⁹.

Preparation of Schiff bases: These were prepared by mixing calculated quantities of the corresponding aldehyde and the amine in ethanolic

medium and the resulting solution was refluxed for 0.5-1 h. On cooling, solidification occurred rapidly. The solids were separated and recrystallised from methylated spirit. The Schiff bases were crystallised as light yellow to orange coloured crystals.

Preparation of complexes: The complexes were prepared by refluxing one part of uranyl nitrate and two parts of Schiff base in ethanolic medium for 1-2 h. On cooling, the orange-red to red coloured complexes were separated, filtered, washed with ethanol and dried (fused CaCl_2) in vacuum.

Analysis: Uranium in the complexes was estimated gravimetrically as U_3O_8 . Nitrogen was estimated by microanalytical method. The results of elemental analysis are given in Table 1.

Physical measurements: The conductance measurements of all the complexes in DMF were made on a Philips PR 9500 conductivity bridge having a cell constant 0.6831 cm^{-1} . Molar conductance of the complexes were calculated (Table 1). The ir spectra (nujol) of the ligands and their

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF URANYL COMPLEXES OF SCHIFF BASES

Ligand	Complex	Colour of complex	Analysis % ; Found (Calcd.)		Conductivity $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
			U	N	
Salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (1)	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{ON}_2)_2]$ (6)	Red	35.32 (35.84)	8.63 (8.43)	*
5-Methyl salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (2)	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2)_2]$ (7)	Red	33.92 (34.39)	8.51 (8.09)	*
Salicylanil (3)	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ (8)	Orange	30.00 (30.20)	7.72 (7.12)	121.031
4'-Nitrosalicylanil (4)	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ (9)	Orange red	26.72 (27.10)	10.00 (9.56)	129.631
3'-Nitrosalicylanil (5)	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2)_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ (10)	Orange	26.64 (27.10)	9.82 (9.56)	127.031

* Insoluble in DMF : Non-electrolytes.

TABLE 2—SELECTED IR FREQUENCY (CM⁻¹) OF SCHIFF'S BASES AND THEIR URANYL COMPLEXES

Compd. no.*	Aromatic C-H stretch	C=N stretch	Aromatic C=C stretch	C=O stretch	OH bending	O-U-O ν ₂	O-NO ₂
1	3 070 w	1 615 sh	1 590 s 1 560 m 1 500 m	1 380 m 1 190 s	1 280 sh	—	—
2	3 070 w	1 610 sh	1 580 s 1 555 s 1 490 m	1 380 m 1 210 s	1 280 s	—	—
3	3 080 w	1 620 s	1 600 sh 1 580 sh 1 485 sh	1 380 sh 1 190 s	1 280 s	—	—
4	—	1 605 sh	1 590 sh 1 570 sh 1 510 sh	1 380 s 1 180 s	1 280 s	—	—
5	3 130 w	1 635 sh	1 615 sh 1 585 sh 1 530 sh	1 385 sh 1 200 sh	1 285 sh	—	—
6	3 100 w	1 625 s	1 600 sh 1 575 sh 1 525 s	1 390 sh 1 190 sh	—	920 s	—
7	3 100 w	1 625 sh	1 595 m 1 575 m 1 545 m	1 380 s 1 210 m	—	905 sh	—
8	3 100 w	1 640 s	1 620 m 1 600 m 1 490 sh	1 390 sh 1 190 m	1 280 s	920 s	1 245 sh
9	3 100 w	1 640 s	1 600 s 1 520 s, b 1 480 sh	1 380 sh 1 180 m	1 280 s	930 s (ν ₂ = 860 sh)	1 240 sh
10	3 130 w	1 660 s	1 630 sh 1 550 s 1 500 m	1 390 m 1 200 m	1 290 s	940 s	1 250 sh

* As in Table 1.

b - broad, m - medium, sh - sharp, s - strong, w - weak.

complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 700 spectrophotometer in the region 4000-650 cm⁻¹ and their tentative assignments are presented in Table 2. From the frequencies of UO₂, the force constant and the bond length values were calculated and reported in Table 3.

TABLE 3—ABSORPTION FREQUENCY, FORCE CONSTANT AND BONDLENGTH VALUES OF URANYL COMPLEXES OF SCHIFF'S BASES

Compd. no.*	ν _{as} O-U-O cm ⁻¹	f _{uo} m dyne/Å	F _{uo} Å
6	920	7.03	1.73
7	905	6.80	1.74
8	920	7.03	1.73
9	930	7.18	1.73
10	940	7.33	1.72

* As in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The complexes obtained are orange-red to red in colour, microcrystalline and are insoluble in common organic solvents. This insolubility hampered the molecular weight determination. However, they are soluble in DMF. The results of elemental analysis (Table 1) suggest that these complexes have 1 : 2 stoichiometry.

Conductance : It is found that the complexes of type-1 are insoluble in DMF and did not permit the conductance measurements and hence can be

regarded as non-electrolytes. It is observed that the molar conductance of the remaining complexes in DMF at the concentration of 10⁻³M fall in the range of 120-130 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ indicating that they behave as 1 : 2 electrolytes. Such results were also observed by Jain *et al.*¹⁰. The DMF solvent molecules displace the weakly coordinated nitrate groups from the coordination sphere¹¹.

Magnetic measurements : Magnetic susceptibilities of the uranyl complexes were measured by a modified form of Gouy's balance, described by Prasad¹². It was observed that all the complexes are diamagnetic in nature. This indicates that all of them are spin-paired complexes of hexavalent uranium.

Infrared spectra : The spectra of Schiff bases and their complexes exhibit a weak band characteristic of aromatic C-H stretching vibration in the region 3 130-3 070 cm⁻¹. In the ligands as well as their complexes, a strong, sharp or medium band is observed in the region 1 630-1 480 cm⁻¹ (C=C stretching). The spectra of the complexes and the ligands show a strong, sharp or medium band in the region 1 390-80 and 1 210-1 180 cm⁻¹ (C=O stretching). Two characteristic frequencies, viz. 940-905 and 860 cm⁻¹, in the complexes, can be predicted^{13,14} for UO₂²⁺ ion. A strong or sharp band is observed for all the reagents in the region 1 285-80 cm⁻¹ (OH bending)¹⁵. This band is also observed in the complexes of type-2.

Absence of measurable absorption in the infrared region characteristic of OH absorption ($3650-3590\text{ cm}^{-1}$) has been attributed to the existence of intra-molecular hydrogen bonding¹⁶.

Some of the Schiff bases studied in the present investigation exhibit the property of thermochromism and photochromism^{17,18}. This property has also been attributed to the existence of intra-molecular hydrogen bonding^{19,20} between the phenolic proton and the imine nitrogen.

The formation of a bond between the oxygen of the OH group and the metal, in all the complexes, increases the electron density on the latter. Consequently, the $\nu_{C=N}$ will shift towards higher wave number side to increase in C—N bond order^{21,22}. A strong and sharp band observed in the region $1635-05\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=N stretch)²³ in the Schiff bases is observed in the region $1660-25\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of the complexes. The observable shift obtained in the C=N stretch after complexing confirms the formation of coordinate bond from oxygen of the OH group and imine nitrogen to the metal ion in the complexes of type-2 and formation of a covalent bond in the complexes of type-1. A sharp band for the complexes of type-2 appearing in the region $1250-40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NO_2 group) is absent in ligands. This band is not observed in the complexes of type-1.

Reagents of type-1 are basic in nature due to the presence of pyridyl nitrogen in their structure. Hence, deprotonation of phenolic hydrogen takes place readily during complexation. A band around 1280 cm^{-1} characteristic of OH bending vibration and absorption characteristic of NO_2 group are absent in the complexes formed from reagents of type-1. These complexes are found to be non-electrolytes as seen from the conductance data. Pyridine nitrogen does not involve⁸ in coordination. All these facts lead to the conclusion that in the complexes derived from reagents of type-1, oxygen of phenol and imine nitrogen are involved in bond formation and also that NO_2 ions are absent. In view of these observations, these complexes can be regarded as having coordination number six. The complexes exhibit a strong band in the region $940-905\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of $\nu_{O=U=O}$. From these, the force constant (f) value of $\nu_{O=U=O}$ and the U—O bond length (R_{U-O}) for all the complexes have been calculated²⁴. The R_{U-O} values fall in the range $1.73-1.74\text{ \AA}$ which are comparable to those ($1.60-1.92\text{ \AA}$) observed for other dioxouranium(VI) complexes²⁵.

With the help of analytical, conductance and infrared spectral data it may be suggested that the Schiff base complexes derived from reagents of type-1 and type-2 have coordination number six

and eight, respectively, and their structures are represented as

Complex type-1

Complex type-2

References

1. M. A. PUJAR and T. D. BHARAMAGOUDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 462.
2. M. D. HODDAY and T. D. SMITH, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1973, 9, 311.
3. O. A. OSIPEV, V. I. MINKIN, D. SH. VERKHOVODOVA and M. I. KNYAZHANSKII, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1968, 68, 87107.
4. N. S. BIRADAR and V. H. KULKARNI, *J. Less-Common Met.*, 1972, 26, 355.
5. K. DEY and K. C. RAY, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1974, 10, 139.
6. S. S. DODWAD, I. R. PATIL and M. G. DATAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 83.
7. S. S. DODWAD, I. R. PATIL and M. G. DATAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 595.
8. P. S. PRABHU and S. S. DODWAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 546.
9. J. C. DUFF, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 547.
10. S. C. JAIN, M. S. GILL and G. S. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 210.
11. J. V. QUAGLIANO, J. FUJITA, G. FRANZ, D. J. PHILLIPS, J. A. WALAMSLAY and S. Y. TYRES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 3370.
12. PRASAD, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1944, 20, 224.
13. J. SELBIN, *Angew. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 712.
14. B. M. GATEHOUSE and A. E. COMYNS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3965.
15. A. M. SHALLABY and M. M. MOSTAFA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, 17, 516.
16. S. P. HENDRICKS, D. R. WULF, G. E. HILBERT and U. LIDDEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1991.

17. M. D. COHEN and G. M. J. SCHMIDT, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 2442.
18. M. D. COHEN, G. M. J. SCHMIDT and S. FLAVIAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 2041.
19. G. M. J. SCHMIDT, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1957, 10, 793.
20. M. D. COHEN, Y. HIRSHOERG and G. M. J. SCHMIDT in "Hydrogen Bonding", ed. D. HADZI, Pergamon Press, London, 1959, p. 293.
21. C. B. SINGH and B. SAHOO, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, 36, 1259.
22. N. S. BIRADAR and V. H. KULKARNI, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1970, 15, 1993.
23. D. H. BUSCH and J. C. BAILAR, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 1137.
24. S. P. MCGLYNN, J. K. SMITH and W. C. NEELY, *J. Chem Phys*, 1961, 35, 105.
25. W. H. ZACHARIASEN, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1954, 8, 847.